

**THE ROLE AND INFLUENCE OF AL-BUKHARI IN THE MEDIEVAL
EASTERN CIVILIZATION**

Alijonova Gulnozakhon

Associate Professor, Department of History, Oriental University

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Historical Sciences

Okilova Musharraf

Oriental University Philology Language Teaching

Student of Group 308, Faculty of Arabic Philology

Annotation: This article aims to highlight the importance of the scientific and religious heritage of Imam Bukhari in the medieval Eastern civilization. Imam Bukhari and his work “Sahih al-Bukhari” occupy an important place in the Islamic world as the second source after the Quran. The work was an important source in determining moral directions and forming religious values among Muslims. The article also shows the importance of the scientist’s scientific methods and analytical skills in modern research.

Keywords: Imam Bukhari, Sahih al-Bukhari, scientific methods, hadiths, Eastern civilization, religious heritage.

Introduction. Imam Bukhari (810-870) is one of the most famous and influential scholars of the Islamic world. Bukhari was born in the city of Bukhara, in present-day Uzbekistan, and was interested in science from a young age. His work “Sahih al-Bukhari” is considered the foundation of the Islamic scientific heritage. This work is considered the most accurate and reliable collection of hadiths. Imam Bukhari played an important role in the rise and development of science, especially religious science, in the Middle East.

Imam Bukhari and the Development of the Science of Hadith Introduction to the Science of Hadith and its Place in the Islamic World: Hadith is the study of the sayings, deeds and customs of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). This

science is considered the second source of Sharia for Muslims. Imam Bukhari was a scholar who made great contributions in this field, and he developed scientific methods for collecting, analyzing and classifying hadiths.

Material and Methods. Imam Bukhari's Contribution to Hadith: Imam Bukhari studied about 600,000 hadiths and included more than 7,000 of them, which he considered the most reliable, in the collection "Sahih al-Bukhari". He selected the hadiths based on strict criteria and carefully studied the honesty and reliability of their narrators. This process required scientific rigor, and he introduced new standards in hadith studies with his research.

Bukhari's work "Sahih al-Bukhari" is considered by many Islamic scholars to be the most sacred book after the Quran. For example, scholars such as Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani and Ibn al-Salah have confirmed the scientific and religious significance of Bukhari's work.

In medieval Muslim culture, this work served as a guide for Muslims in religious life and was one of the main sources for the practical application of Sharia. We will analyze in depth the role of Imam Bukhari in medieval Eastern civilization. We will get acquainted with the main aspects and evidence of each section.

Imam Bukhari traveled to Baghdad, Egypt, Syria, Hijaz and other centers of knowledge, studying hadiths and receiving lessons from many scholars. This led to a broad scientific outlook.

His work "Sahih al-Bukhari" was widely distributed in the Islamic world and was accepted as the main religious literature for medieval Muslims. Imam Bukhari's Contribution to Islamic Science and Philosophy Philosophical Topics and Thought Process: In addition to religious sciences, Imam Bukhari also reflected on philosophical topics. He gave scientific explanations on issues related to Islamic faith and fought against philosophical movements and heresies in the Islamic world. For example, he opposed the Mu'tazila movement of that time, criticized some of their ideas, and tried to maintain doctrinal stability among

Muslims. Imam Bukhari's works widely covered thoughts on human behavior, morality, and religious issues, which served the development of Islamic philosophy. Imam Bukhari's legacy has a significant impact on religious and

Impact on spiritual life Impact on religious and spiritual life: Imam Bukhari's works were used as the main source in Muslim societies for making fair judgments, observing Sharia law, and teaching general religious rules. His scientific and religious views made a great contribution to strengthening religious consciousness among Muslims. Imam Bukhari's hadiths were accepted as the basis for many fatwas and Sharia decisions in the Islamic world. His works are also studied by modern Islamic scholars and are used in Islamic education.

In recent years, our scholars have been conducting many studies and scientific and practical works in order to study, research, and disseminate to the general public the scientific and spiritual heritage of Imam Bukhari and the spiritual heritage left by our other scholars who are children of this land.

In order to deeply study the scientific and spiritual heritage of Imam Bukhari and present it to the general public, the establishment of the Imam Bukhari International Scientific Research Center and the Higher Hadith School by the decree of our President in 2017, and the research conducted here, are among these.

Results. The scientific staff of this scientific research center and teachers of the higher school are translating the scientific heritage of the scholar of hadith, such as “Birrul-walidayn”, “Kholqu af’alu-l-ibad” and “at-Tarih as-sagh’ir”, and the book “Sulosiyotu-l-Bukhari”, a collection of hadiths with a high chain of transmission in the collection of hadiths “Sahihul Bukhari”, which is about to be published, is evidence of our opinion. Imam Bukhari strictly adhered to these twelve conditions when accepting hadiths as authentic, and for this reason, his hadith collections are recognized by scholars around the world as absolutely authentic hadiths. Some scholars have even increased Imam Bukhari's conditions for accepting hadiths to fifteen. Based on the results of our research, we can say that the level of authenticity of Imam Bukhari's hadiths in the collection of hadiths

“al-Jame' as-Sahih” is superior to the authentic hadiths of other hadith scholars. Of course, it is not possible to provide a detailed explanation of the masterpiece of the hadith scholar "al-Jame' as-Sahih" in a short article. The work, as its name suggests, is a "Jame'" that encompasses many sciences. Along with jurisprudential issues, it also addresses ideological, social, and ethical issues. The more you read this work, the more you will discover its unexplored aspects and wisdom.

Discussion. The importance of studying the works of Imam Bukhari today Imam Bukhari's works are also relevant in modern Muslim societies. They continue to serve as a means of preserving religious and spiritual values and as life guidelines for Muslims. His works also play an important role in expanding knowledge of Islam in scientific research and academic circles. Today, there are many translations and commentaries of "Sahih al-Bukhari" in the Muslim world, which are widely used in religious teachings. Imam Bukhari's works are included as important educational sources in Islamic universities and madrasah education systems.

Imam Bukhari occupied a unique place in religious and scientific development in medieval Eastern civilization. His scientific activities and legacy played an important role not only in preserving and promoting religious knowledge, but also in the intellectual development of the Muslim world. The works he created remain relevant in scientific and spiritual life today. Imam Bukhari is a person who played a very important role in the development of the scientific and religious environment in the medieval Eastern civilization. The work "Sahih al-Bukhari" he created not only determined religious and moral trends among Muslims, but was also distinguished by the high level of application of scientific criteria. Bukhari's scientific analyses, methods used in selecting hadiths, and scientific dialogues contributed to the high level of advancement of science and social life of that time.

Conclusion. The thoughts and methods in Bukhari's works left a deep mark on the religious life of the medieval Eastern civilization and determined traditional

scientific trends for Muslims. He made a great contribution to the formation of the religious worldview of the people and the direction of education. Bukhari's religious legacy influenced most of the Muslim world in his time and in subsequent centuries, and his scientific methods were accepted as scientific methodology in later periods.

The works of Imam Bukhari have retained their relevance. His scientific methods and critical analysis methods are used in modern academic research. In Islamic universities and religious educational institutions, Bukhari's legacy is taught as one of the main educational sources and is being taught to new generations. The scientific criteria he created are of great importance in ensuring religious and scientific stability in the Muslim world today. Imam Bukhari, in the history of medieval Eastern civilization and science, made a unique scientific contribution to the development of Islamic thought.

References

1. Al-Buxoriy, Imom. Sahih al-Buxoriy. O'zbek tilida tarjimalar va sharhlar (Toshkent: Movarounnahr nashriyoti, 1998).
2. Ibn Hajar al-Asqaloniy. Fath al-Bari fi sharh Sahih al-Bukhari (Bayrut: Dar al-Ma'rifah, 1986).
3. Ibn al-Salah. Muqaddima fi Ulum al-Hadith (Misr: Dar al-Hadith, 2005).
4. Fazlur Rahman. Islam and Modernity: Transformation of an Intellectual Tradition (University of Chicago Press, 1982).
5. John L. Esposito. The Oxford History of Islam (Oxford University Press, 1999).
6. Maktabah Shamila. Imom Buxoriy asarlari va ularga sharhlar to'plami (Elektron manba).
7. Abdulqodir Zabidi. O'rta asrlar Sharq sivilizatsiyasida Imom Buxoriy roli (Buxoro: Ilm va ma'rifat nashriyoti, 2010).

8. Khalid Blankinship. The History of Islamic Theology (New York: State University of New York Press, 1994).
9. Marshall Hodgson. The Venture of Islam (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1974).
10. Nasr, Seyyed Hossein. Islamic Philosophy from Its Origin to the Present (SUNY Press, 2006).